

Title:

Influence of Age and Comorbidities on the Severity of Coronary Artery Disease: A Cross-Sectional Study from a Tertiary Care Center in India

Abstract:

Background: Coronary artery disease (CAD) severity is commonly stratified into single-vessel disease (SVD), double-vessel disease (DVD), and triple-vessel disease (TVD). The contribution of age and comorbid conditions such as hypertension (HTN) and type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) to CAD complexity remains underexplored in Indian populations.

Methods: A cross-sectional observational study was conducted on 75 patients undergoing coronary angiography at a tertiary care hospital. Patients were grouped into three age categories: 25–45, 46–65, and 66–90 years. Data on comorbidities (HTN and T2DM), demographic characteristics, and angiographic findings were collected. Statistical analysis assessed the association between age, comorbidities, and CAD severity.

Results: Of 75 patients, 26 had SVD (34.7%), 22 had DVD (29.3%), and 27 had TVD (36%). SVD predominated in patients aged 25–45 (56%), whereas TVD was more prevalent in the 46–65 (48%) and 66–90 (52%) age groups. HTN was present in 36 patients and associated with a higher frequency of TVD (44%). T2DM, observed in 24 patients, was also linked to increased DVD and TVD incidence. Chi-square analysis confirmed a significant association between age and vessel disease severity ($p = 0.0057$).

Conclusion: Increasing age and the presence of comorbidities such as HTN and T2DM significantly correlate with higher CAD complexity. Middle age (46–65 years) emerged as a critical period for disease escalation, underscoring the need for early risk factor management to mitigate severe CAD progression.